

TABLE

No.	R ₁	R ₂	m.p. °C	% Nitrogen	
				Calculated	Found
I	Phenyl	Phenyl	259-62	18.4	18.5
II	Phenyl	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	234-36	17.7	17.7
III	Phenyl	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	277-78	17.7	17.6
IV	Phenyl	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	294-96	16.7	16.4
V	Phenyl	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	245-47	16.6	16.4
VI	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	Phenyl	311-13	17.7	17.6
VII	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	246-47	16.8	17.2
VIII	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	185-87	16.8	17.1
IX	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	260-63	16.8	16.8
X	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Phenyl	303-05	16.6	16.2
XI	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	163-64	15.9	16.2
XII	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	252-55	15.0	15.4
XIII	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	Phenyl	184-85	16.8	17.0
XIV	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	180-82	16.1	16.3
XV	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	186-87	15.2	15.6

kept at 110° for 2 hr, cooled and poured into ice-cold 2*N* aqueous hydrochloric acid (100 ml.). The separated solid was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether mixture; m.p. 143-45°; yield = 5.5 g.

1,5-diphenylpyrazolo [3,4-d]-pyrimidine-4,6-dione :

II (3.5 g; 0.01 mole) in absolute alcohol (40 ml.) containing 0.25 g of sodium, was kept under reflux for 2 hr. Alcohol was distilled off under reduced pressure and to the residue was added 100 ml. of water. The insoluble part was filtered off and the clear aqueous solution was acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The separated solid was crystallised from aqueous alcohol; m.p. 259-61°; yield = 2.1 g. Found : N, 18.51; C₁₇H₁₂N₄O₂ requires : N, 18.42%.

Acknowledgement

Our thanks are due to Dr. V. Srinivasan, Director, Sarabhai Research Centre, for his keen interest in this work.

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Nitrogen Transport during Non-Faradaic Electrolysis

SANTI R. PALIT, SUSANTA K. SENGUPTA and
RABINDRA NATH DAS

Department of Physical Chemistry,
Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Jadavpur,
Calcutta-700032.

Manuscript received 10 December 1975, accepted 29
January 1976

PALIT has demonstrated^{1,2} that electrolysis of dilute solutions at low current density gives results apparently incompatible with Faraday's law. He calls it non-Faradaic electrolysis, the following three anomalies being its main features^{1,2}: (i) Volume deficit, (ii) Ratio anomaly and (iii) Co-liberation (i.e., liberation of H₂ and O₂ together on the same electrode). Some independent confirmations of these anomalies are now forthcoming^{4,5}.

However under the same conditions if the electrolysis is done in an open-to-air type cell as shown in Figure 1 both the electrode gases contain a considerable proportion of nitrogen³. Furthermore, Palit has reported³ that if in the intermediate portion of a cell which is evidently quite away from the electrodes are kept enclosed some electroneutral gases such as nitrogen or argon, the latter get transported out of this

Fig. 1.

intermediate zone. The matter has been taken up for closer study and herein is given the preliminary results of the same.

Experimental

A modified cell design (Fig. 1) has been used in which either one or both of the electrode chambers

get connected to the central non-electrode zone exposed to air by a 1.5 cm long fine side tube capillary (1 mm dia.). The electrolysis cell was kept immersed in a thermostat at 60°. A millinormal potassium sulphate was used as the electrolyte and the nitrogen assay in the liberated gas was made by difference after analysing it separately for hydrogen and oxygen. For the purpose of comparison a coulometric cell containing (N) K₂SO₄ was run in series.

Some representative data are presented in Table I from which it is easily seen that nitrogen from air gets copiously transported both to the cathode as well as to the anode. The following points are worthy of note.

(a) There is an innate preference of such nitrogen transport towards the anode than towards the cathode. Nitrogen is always found in the anode gas even when the anode chamber is isolated through a fine capillary (of course in a smaller proportion), whereas with the same kind of isolation of the cathode chamber nitrogen is practically absent in the cathode gas.

(b) Lower the strength of current used, greater is the extent of such nitrogen transport to the electrode zones.

Discussion

It may be thought at first sight that nitrogen found in electrode gases is simply the bubbled-out dissolved nitrogen caused by some physical disturbance at the electrode areas due to gas liberation there. However, this is discounted by a number of facts: (i) Greater current strength (i.e., more bubbling) lowers the nitrogen content; (ii) Nitrogen proportion in anode gas is greater than that in cathode gas; and (iii) By suitable barriering there can be observed total absence of nitrogen in the cathode gas under otherwise favourable conditions (see Table I) and (iv) It has been found that on continuous bubbling of hydrogen and oxygen at cathode and anode sites

TABLE I. RESULTS ON N₂ TRANSPORT DURING ELECTROLYSIS

Electrolyte (conc.)	Current (mA)	V _{FC} (ml)	Cathode chamber	Anode chamber	%N ₂ in cathode gas	%N ₂ in anode gas	V _C (ml)	V _A (ml)
N/1000 K ₂ SO ₄	5	41.8	Fitted with side capillary.	Without side capillary	Nil	57.9	40.4*	12.8
"	5	28.0	Without side capillary	Fitted with side capillary.	42.6	5.0	17.8*	14.8
"	5	49.5	-do-	Without side capillary	35.1	54.8	36.7*	14.0*
"	5	17.6	Fitted with side capillary.	Fitted with side capillary.	Nil	9.3	17.5*	9.0
"	1	33.7	-do-	Without side capillary	1.4	73.0	38.5*	5.9
"	1	33.7	Without side capillary.	Fitted with side capillary.	59.1	7.1	19.1*	19.1*
"	1	26.6	Fitted with side capillary.	-do-	6.1	16.8	29.6*	15.4

* Indicates co-liberation of H₂ and O₂ in the liberated gas.

NOTES

respectively, no nitrogen could be found in the bubbled-out gases.

It is evident that the source of this nitrogen lies outside the electrode chambers. Now, the question arises how it gets transported to the electrodes. Obviously, it is extremely difficult to conceive of such nitrogen transport in the light of conventional concept of electrolytic current conduction. However, from the characteristics of the phenomenon as enumerated, one can confidently surmise that the process is intimately associated with non-Faradaic electrolytic process. It appears that the idea that a substantial fraction of current under low current and low ion concentration conditions is carried by unconventional carriers such as charged microbubbles, charged water molecules or their clusters, may be involved. Such charged species are likely to have a role in this phenomenon. Such micellar species in course of their journey through inter-electrode electrolyte may dissolve (in the case of charged water molecules) or encapsule (in the case of microbubbles) nitrogen (from dissolved air) which they meet on their way and transport them to the electrodes. The differential extent of current conduction among such cationic and anionic species may result in the difference of nitrogen observed in cathode and anode gases. Lower the current strength, greater is the

degree of conduction by such species and higher is the proportion of nitrogen in the electrode gases.

It is to be further pointed out that the observed substantial reduction in nitrogen content and also of co-liberation (not reported here) in the liberated gas, on isolating any or both the electrode chambers by means of a small capillary (1.5 cm long and 1 mm dia.) is not due to the mechanical barriering by the capillary but is related to the distribution of potential gradient. What needs to be emphasized is that small size of the opening does not seem to be the causative factor here as it has been observed that even with interposition of polythene membrane of pore size as small as $100\text{\AA}$ usual non-Faradaic features including co-liberation persist to a considerable degree⁵.

References

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